

Oxygen Evolution on Aged IrO_x/Ti Electrodes. I. Acidic Solutions

HUIMIN CHEN** and S. TRASATTI*

Department of Physical Chemistry and Electrochemistry, University of Milan, Via Venezian 21, 20133 Milan, Italy
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The effect of ageing and of the electrolyte anion in O₂ evolution on IrO_x/Ti electrodes has been studied in H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ solutions with IrO_x electrodes, prepared by thermal decomposition at 300-500^o, already used for over two years under cathodic conditions. The influence of the storage conditions (water vs air) has also been investigated. Results have shown that the Tafel slope is lower in HClO₄ and that the *true* electrocatalytic activity increases at lower calcination temperatures. Ageing improves the electrode activity, especially for water-stored samples. A general mechanism is proposed. IrO_x electrodes do not show serious signs of erosion under anodic load in acidic solutions.

IrO_x(nominally IrO₂) prepared by thermal decomposition of the chloride is an active electrocatalyst for O₂ evolution¹. IrO_x can also be obtained by electrolytic growth on the parent metal², although in this form it is subjected to anodic dissolution, or by reactive sputtering³. There appears to exist consistent evidence that IrO_x is (though little) less active than RuO_x⁴⁻⁶, although the former can stabilise the latter against anodic dissolution⁷. IrO_x in a mixture with RuO_x is thus recommended for oxygen evolving anodes especially in aggressive acidic environments. The reported activity of IrO_x in acidic solution spans however over a broad range, the Tafel slope varying between as low values as 35 mV up to 70 mV^{2,4,5,7-14}. On average, the Tafel slope is probably higher than that of RuO_x, but the reasons for the large variety of results are still unclear. Table 1 summarises the data available in the literature. It is interesting that all the experiments were conducted in H₂SO₄ solution.

In a previous work dealing with IrO_x + RuO_x mixtures, we obtained a Tafel slope of 60 mV for O₂ evolution from 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄⁵. However, the electrodes were freshly prepared, and the effect of the calcination temperature was not in-

vestigated. In view of the varied experimental picture, it has been deemed of interest to study the O₂ evolution reaction on 'aged' IrO_x electrodes, i.e. samples with an extended operative life. Further, the effect of the electrolyte anion has been explored by comparing H₂SO₄ with HClO₄ solutions.

TABLE 1— KINETIC STUDIES OF O₂ EVOLUTION ON IrO_x IN ACIDIC SOLUTION

Preparation	Electrolyte <i>M</i> H ₂ SO ₄	<i>T</i> (°C)	<i>b</i> (mV)
Sputtered ^f	0.5	25	70 → 210
Thermal ^h	1.0	30	70
Electrolytic ^c	0.5	room	50
Electrolytic ^d	1.0	25	54 → 127
Electrolytic ^e	0.5	room	50
Sputtered ^f	0.5	room	58
Thermal/Ti ^g	1.0	50	100 → 160
/TiO ₂ ^g	1.0	50	30-80 → 60-120
Thermal ^h	0.5	30	57
Thermal ⁱ	0.5	25	35 → 55
Thermal ⁱ	0.5	25	60
Electrolytic ^l	0.5	room	40
↳ heated ^k	0.5	room	60 → 160

*The arrow indicates a transition at higher current density.
^aRef.8. ^bRef.9 ^cRef.10 ^dRef.2. ^eRef.4 ^fRef.7 ^gRef.11. ^hRef.12
ⁱRef.13 ^jRef.5 ^kRef.14.

** Permanent address : Fujian Institute of Research on the Structure of Matter, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Fuzhou, Fujian, P. R. China.

Results and Discussion

A voltammetric study of the electrodes used in this work has been presented in a previous paper¹⁵. Structural and electric properties have been reported elsewhere¹⁷. Previous results have shown¹⁶ that stable IrO_x is formed at calcination temperatures $\geq 400^\circ$. The behaviour under cathodic load is dramatically different depending on whether or not stable IrO_x is formed¹⁸. The results of the present work show that this is not the case under anodic conditions, although the kind of storage may have a definite influence.

Voltammetric charge : The interpretation of voltammetric curves has been discussed in previous papers^{15,18}. In this work voltammetric curves were measured between groups of experiments in order to monitor the state of the electrode surface. The voltammetric charge has been shown to be a relative measure of the active surface area and can thus be useful to separate electronic from geometric effects²⁰, as well as to follow any modification in the electrode morphology²¹.

TABLE 2 – INITIAL VOLTAMMETRIC CHARGE OF IrO_x IN ACIDIC SOLUTION*

Temp of calcination/ $^\circ\text{C}$	Charge, q^* (mC cm^{-2})	
	Stored in water	Stored in air
300	Passive	Passive
330	100	45
360	262	26
400	81	78
450	120	86
500	76	97

*At the beginning of the present study, O_2 evolution was studied first in H_2SO_4 solution and then in HClO_4 solution.

Table 2 summarises the charge data at the beginning of this work. While the dependence of q^* on the calcination temperature is discussed elsewhere^{15,16}, it is here stressed the dramatic effect of the storage conditions at $T_c < 400^\circ$. Electrodes prepared at 300° showed clear signs of passivation indicating that the coating was so deteriorated by previous studies as to uncover the Ti support. With electrodes prepared at 330 and 360° , the value of q^* is much higher for those stored in water. This indicates that the layer of those stored in air has been seriously

eroded with loss of material. While erosion is probably related to the mechanical action of gas evolution during previous studies, the generally lower stability of air-stored samples is likely to indicate lower adhesion between crystallites. Thus, a hydrous surface appears to induce stronger adhesion between neighbouring particles.

Such an effect is of minor importance for electrodes prepared at $T_c \geq 400^\circ$, probably because of higher compactness of the active layer.

Tafel plots : Fig. 1 shows typical Tafel plots

Fig. 1. Uncorrected Tafel plots for O_2 evolution on a IrO_x/Ti electrode calcined at 450° and stored in water : (1) $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ and (2) $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$

for the same electrode in H_2SO_4 and HClO_4 solutions. Oxygen evolution starts at about 1.2 V (SCE), the activity being initially higher in H_2SO_4 solution. Since the Tafel slope appears slightly higher in the sulphate solution, the two curves intersect at more anodic potentials and the activity becomes eventually higher in HClO_4 solutions. The two curves in Fig. 1 are distorted by uncompensated ohmic drops. These have not been corrected in the raw data since the practical performance of an electrode is characterised by the actual potential value. However, in order to elucidate the reaction mechanism, IR-correction has been performed using an approach suggested by Shub *et al.*^{22,23}. This consists in drawing a Tafel line from the low current density points and in computing at each current value the ΔE between the raw potential value and the derived straight line.

Fig. 2. shows a typical example of ΔE vs I

Fig.2. Apparent IR drop as a function of current for O_2 evolution on a IrO_x/Ti electrode calcined at 400° and stored in air : (1) $1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$ and (2) $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

plot. For the same electrode ohmic drop is higher in H_2SO_4 than in $HClO_4$ solution. This reflects higher conductivity of the molar solution of $HClO_4$. However, the single straight line obtained passing through the origin indicates that there exists only one Tafel slope up to 0.2 A, the highest current reached in this work. This appears to be generally the case with all the electrodes.

The existence of a single Tafel slope is demonstrated in Fig. 3 beyond doubt for the electrode whose ΔE vs I data are collected in Fig. 2. It is interesting that the correction looks quite accurate all over the current range. Fig. 3 also shows a comparison with some of our previous studies with fresh electrodes⁵. RuO_x still appears more active even than 'aged' IrO_x , but the latter exhibits a lower Tafel slope than fresh IrO_x , in particular without the rise at higher current densities which is visible in the previous data.

Tafel slope : Tafel slopes (b) were determined graphically in the current density range $j < 1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ where ohmic drop corrections are negligible. The values reported refer to the second forward and the second backward polarisation curve.

Fig.4 shows the effect of the calcination temperature as well as of the storage conditions in H_2SO_4

Fig. 3. Uncorrected (\blacksquare) and IR -corrected (\times) Tafel plots for O_2 evolution from $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ on a IrO_x/Ti electrode calcined at 400° and stored in air: (1) RuO_x^5 , and (2) IrO_x^5 .

Fig. 4. Tafel slopes from forward and backward Tafel lines for O_2 evolution from $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ on IrO_x/Ti electrodes calcined at different temperatures : (\blacktriangle) electrodes stored in water and (\blacktriangledown) electrodes stored in air.

solution. The Tafel slope is seen to vary between 40 and 60 mV with a trend to increase as the calcination temperature increases. There is a sharp rise at $T_c > 400^\circ$. On the whole, the Tafel slope is higher for electrodes stored in air, although the difference reduces as the calcination temperature increases. No systematic difference is observed between forward and backward curve.

The situation in $HClO_4$ solution is illustrated in Fig. 5. A generally lower Tafel slope is observed, b increasing from about 35 to about 50 mV as

T_c increases. A lower value for the electrodes stored in water is observed in this case as well. It is to be noted that most of the results in the literature (cf Table 1) have been obtained with electrodes not intentionally stored in water. Therefore, the results for air-stored samples are more appropriate for comparison with literature data.

The data in Figs.4 and 5 indicate that O_2 evolu-

Fig. 5. Tafel slopes from forward and backward Tafel lines for O_2 evolution from 1 mol dm^{-3} $HClO_4$ on IrO_x/Ti electrodes calcined at different temperatures: (▲) electrodes stored in water and (▼) electrodes stored in air.

tion proceeds in H_2SO_4 solution with a different mechanism from that in $HClO_4$ solution. This may be related to the stronger adsorbability of sulphate ions on the IrO_x surface, as observed previously by potentiometric titration²⁴.

Reaction order : The way the reaction order was determined (cf the Experimental section) allowed E_{oc} to be measured as a function of pH. Normally, several hours elapsed between experiments in two different solutions.

Fig. 6 shows a typical example of dependence of E_{oc} on the H^+ concentration (since experiments were conducted at constant ionic strength, the activity coefficient of H^+ can be assumed constant to a first approximation). In either solution (H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$) the electrodes stored in air exhibit a pH dependence of ca 0.06 V per unit as observed in previous studies¹⁹, while no effect of the electrolyte

Fig. 6. open-circuit potential vs $\log c_{H^+}$ during reaction order determination experiments for O_2 evolution from 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 on IrO_x/Ti electrodes calcined at 500° and stored in water (▼) and in air (▲), respectively.

on E_{oc} can be recognised. However, the value of E_{oc} is, for water-stored samples, much more positive than expected. This suggests that water-stored electrodes do not equilibrate with the solution during the time of the open-circuit step, so that the measured value is still reminiscent of the extensive O_2 evolution to which the samples were subjected in the previous run, even if several hours before. Air-stored samples, on the contrary, lose readily the higher oxidation state once emerged from the solution.

Fig. 7 shows the dependence of current density on the H^+ concentration in H_2SO_4 and $HClO_4$ respectively, for the same electrode. While the current at the same potential is slightly higher in sulphate solution (as expected, cf Fig. 1), the pH dependence is the same. In particular, the slope is definitely higher than 1 but lower than 2, probably close to 1.5.

The fractional reaction order, though observed with all electrodes, depends slightly on the calcination temperature. Fig. 8 shows that the reaction order in H_2SO_4 solution is probably a little lower at the highest temperature of calcination, consistently with the different Tafel slope (cf Fig. 4). In view of the scatter of data and of the differential nature of this quantity, no systematic dependence of the reaction order on the storage conditions can be recognised.

Fig. 7. Log-log plot of current density at 1.2 V (SCE) vs H^+ concentration for O_2 evolution on IrO_x/Ti electrodes calcined at 500° and stored in air : (■) 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 and (□) 1 mol dm^{-3} $HClO_4$. Straight lines of slope 1 and 1.5 are drawn.

Fig. 8. Apperent reaction order (ν_{H^+}) as a function of the calcination temperature of IrO_x/Ti electrodes for O_2 evolution from 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 solutions: (▲) electrodes stored in water and (▼) electrodes stored in air.

Activity and surface area : Since the activity of catalysts depends on both electronic and geometric factors, decisive insight into the electrocatalytic properties of materials can only be gained by operating a separation of the two effects. For oxide electrodes, this can be achieved by comparing activity with voltammetric charge, the latter being regarded as proportional to the active surface area^{18,20}.

Fig.9 shows a plot of current density at constant potential as a function of voltammetric charge. While

the points for H_2SO_4 solution lie above those for $HClO_4$ solution, the two groups of data gather approximately around two straight lines. This suggests, to a first approximation, proportionality between activity and active surface, i.e. geometric effect only.

The scatter of data in Fig. 9 might in fact

Fig.9. Current density at 1.2 V (SCE) as a function of the voltammetric charge for O_2 evolution on IrO_x/Ti electrodes from (1) 1 mol dm^{-3} $HClO_4$ and (2) 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 : (▲, △) electrodes stored in water and (▼, ▽) electrodes stored in air.

conceal more subtle effects. In Fig. 10, the apparent current density has been divided by the voltammetric

Fig.10. Current density at 1.25 V (SCE) per unit surface charge from Tafel plots for O_2 evolution as a function of calcination temperature of IrO_x/Ti electrodes : (▲, ▽) 1 mol dm^{-3} $HClO_4$ and (▲, ▼) 0.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 : (▲, △) electrodes stored in water and (▼, ▽) electrodes stored in air.

charge (which should result in a quantity depending on the *true* electrocatalytic activity only), and plotted as a function of calcination temperature. Two new features are thus disclosed for the *true* electrocatalytic activity: (i) it is higher for electrodes stored in water, and (ii) it shows a trend to increase as the calcination temperature decreases. However, the effect of the storage conditions tends to vanish in H₂SO₄ solution for electrodes calcined at $T_c > 400^\circ$.

If the data in Fig.10 are normalised to the lower value of activity in each series, Fig. 11

Fig.11. Data of the previous plots normalised to the lowest value of (j/q^*) of each series.

shows that at $T_c < 400^\circ$ the trend to increase is approximately independent of the electrolyte nature and of the storage conditions.

Stability: The voltammetric charge gives a relative measure of the active surface of the electrodes. If q^* is measured before and after use, its variation can provide some insight into the stability of the electrode surface²¹.

Fig. 12 shows a plot of the initial value of q^* against its final value after the O₂ evolution studies in both H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ solution. The data show that in either solution, there is a small but definite decrease of q^* amounting to no more than a few percent. A decrease in q^* indicates, in view of the proportionality between charge and oxide loading, loss of material, i.e. erosion. The amount is almost the same in the two electrolytes which implies that no anion-induced dissolution

Fig.12. Plot of the voltammetric charge at the beginning (i) and at the end (f) of the O₂ evolution studies with IrO_x/Ti electrodes: (○) 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ and (●) 1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄.

mechanism is operating. Erosion is very likely to be related to mechanical effects of the evolving O₂ gas. In this respect, air-stored samples calcined at $T_c < 400^\circ$ are probably less stable, but the evidence is inconclusive. To a first approximation, the stability for O₂ evolution is independent of the storage conditions.

Conclusions: O₂ evolution takes place on IrO_x electrodes with a mechanism whose details depend on the calcination temperature, the storage conditions and the electrolyte anion. Comparison with literature data shows that 'aged' electrodes behave somewhat differently from the fresh ones since they exhibit a lower Tafel slope.

The apparent higher current at low overpotential in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution is to be related to the slightly higher pH of this solution with respect to 1 M HClO₄ (0.5 vs 0.2). However, the higher Tafel slope in the presence of sulphates is probably due to the strongest adsorbability of these ions. Therefore, the 'normalised' activity of IrO_x for O₂ evolution is eventually lower in sulphate-containing solutions.

The consistently observed Tafel slope of 60 mV in previous work appears to be related to the use of fresh electrodes in H₂SO₄ solution. On the other hand, the Tafel slope is lower on anodically grown IrO_x¹⁴. Since anodic oxides are 'hydrated' (practically,

hydroxide-like)^{25,26}, the activating effects of a lower calcination temperature and of water-storage conditions are to be associated with to a more 'hydrous' nature of water-stored and of low- T_c electrodes. On the other hand, the previous use of these electrodes for H₂ evolution studies¹⁷ may well have increased their hydrous structure thus resulting in a generalised lowering of the Tafel slope.

There is a continuous transition of the Tafel slope from less than 40 mV to about 60 mV as T_c is increased, and HClO₄ is substituted for H₂SO₄. This may indicate a smooth transition between two rate-determining steps in the same general mechanism²⁷ :

OH* is assumed to be an unreactive intermediate whose rearrangement on the oxide surface is a requirement for further oxidation. Step (1b) might involve 'spillover' effects: these are probably impeded by sulphate adsorption, which makes step (1b) to be rate-determining (60 mV Tafel slope) in H₂SO₄ solution. On the other hand, it appears that a more hydroxylated active layer facilitates step (1b).

As step (1b) becomes faster, step (1c) starts to determine the reaction rate. The Tafel slope decreases eventually tending to 40 mV (second electron transfer as r.d.s.). Steps (1a) and (1b) may compete at higher overpotential and a second Tafel slope of 120 mV may appear as step (1a) becomes rate-determining. This is in fact what has been observed in previous studies⁵. The single Tafel slope observed in this work suggests that 'ageing' and 'hydrophilisation' of the electrode surface may facilitate step (1a). This implies that the adsorption of the intermediate is less favourable on fresh surfaces, i.e. it is probably weaker.

A fractional reaction order has been observed in previous studies with oxides and has been shown to be a manifestation of the surface acid-base equilibrium which these materials establish with protonated solutions^{28,29}. As already demonstrated elsewhere, the value of the apparent reaction order depends on the value of the apparent transfer coefficient. This explains the variability of the experimental reaction order. The chemically significant reaction order is in all case -1, in accord with mechanism (1).

There is a definite increase by a factor of 2 to 3 in the true electrocatalytic activity as the calcination temperature is decreased, and by another factor of 2 to 3 if electrodes are stored in water. Considering geometric effects, electrodes prepared at 360° and stored in water are thus among the most active ones.

In a previous paper¹⁷, it has been shown that at 360° electrodes are not active for H₂ evolution while the samples stored in air are mechanically unstable under cathodic load. On the contrary, besides being very active, electrodes prepared at low T_c are also stable towards O₂ evolution. This can be understood in terms of OH bridges binding the crystallites together under anodic conditions, thus imparting stability even to air-stored electrodes.

Experimental

IrO_x was prepared by thermal decomposition of hydrated IrCl₃ in the temperature (T_c) range 300–500° as described previously^{15,16}. The electrodes used in the present work were not freshly prepared, but they had already been subjected to extensive cathodic investigations both in acidic and in alkaline solutions for more than 3 years. During their whole life, the electrodes were split into two sets: between experiments, one was permanently stored in pure water, while the other one was currently kept in the laboratory air. As put forward previously¹⁵, the idea was to observe the influence of the degree of macroscopic wetting on the electrocatalytic performances.

Electrodes were prepared at $T_c = 300, 330, 360, 400, 450, \text{ and } 500^\circ$. Two electrodes were

prepared at each temperature (one stored in water, the other in air). A total of 12 electrodes were prepared.

Kinetic experiments were carried out as described previously¹⁷ at 25° in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ and in 1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ solutions respectively, prepared with Fluka reagents (purum p.a.) and Milli-Q water. Unless otherwise specified, current density was based on the apparent (geometric) surface area. Electrode potentials were read (and are reported) on the SCE scale.

The order of reaction with respect to OH⁻ was determined by single-point experiments using the following potential sequence: read the open-circuit potential (E_{oc}), bring the electrode to 1.05 V (5 min), step to 1.2 V, read the current after 3 min, back to 1.05 V (5min), read E_{oc} . The composition of the solution was varied between 0.05 and 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄, and between 0.1 and 1 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄, keeping the ionic strength constant by means of Na₂SO₄ and NaClO₄ respectively.

The state of the electrode surface was monitored between different experiments by recording the voltammetric curve at 20 mV s⁻¹ in the potential range 0.15 – 1.15 V (SCE).

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